

QUIZ**LAST NAME: BREUNIG****FIRST NAME: MARIA MAGDALENA****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT**1. Which of the following options is not considered plagiarism?**

- Writing about common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.¹**
- Copy-pasting from the Internet where no author is mentioned.
- Changing up a sentence structure from the original source to avoid the need of citing the source.
- Mentioning other author's ideas without using his exact words to avoid the need of citing the source.

2. Which is the correct way to cite the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1 in a bibliography?

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2019, ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5–10

- Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.**²
- Euclid University. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

3. **Which of the following aspects are not regulated in a style guide?**

- Manuscript layout.
- Spelling.
- Accepted terminology.
- Manuscript length.**³

4. **Which of the following words is misspelt?**

- Hurrying.
- Happyness**⁴
- Beautiful.
- Ladies.

5. **Point out the word spelled in British English.**

- Aging.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, II.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 24–25.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 411.

- Color.
- Centre.**⁵
- Raise.

6. **Which of the following sentences are correct according to the Chicago Rule of Style?**

- We analyzed sixty-two cases; of these, fifty-nine had occurred in adults and three in children.
- We analyzed 62 cases; of these, 59 had occurred in adults and three in children.
- We analysed 62 cases; of these 59 had occurred in adults & 3 in children.
- We analyzed 62 cases; of these, 59 had occurred in adults and 3 in children.**⁶

7. **Which information is considered raw data?**

- 234 of the 400 participants of group A developed symptoms.**⁷
- The research has a significant outcome.
- The research was conducted according to scientific standards.
- All participants signed a consent form before participating in the research.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 28.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 198–99.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 10-11.

8. Which of the following sentences commits the mistake of anthropomorphism?

- The researchers found that the workers were not satisfied with their income.
- Clients can go to the clinic for family health to receive services.
- The research found that the workers were not satisfied with their income. 8**
- The staff of the clinic for family health will provide best practice services.

9. How many member states does the UN have?

- 190.
- 193.⁹**
- 152.
- 199.

10. Which sentence is written in a non-discriminatory manner?

- Many children are malnourished in underdeveloped countries.
- The NGO provides support to the handicapped.
- Each researcher is responsible for writing his own report.
- The supervisor worked together with a team of research scientists.¹⁰**

⁸ Turabian et al., 10.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: WHO, 2004), 85–93.

¹⁰ WHO, 55-58.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. 4th ed. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.